

***In silico* evaluation of *Mimosa pudica*'s bioactive compounds as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors for hypertension**

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is a major cause of death globally. Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors are used to treat hypertension; however, the ACE inhibitors that are available on the market are expensive, which creates an economic toll on patients, especially in the Philippines. A potential solution is to explore cost-effective alternatives, such as *Mimosa pudica*, because it contains antihypertensive properties. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the bioactive compounds isolated from *Mimosa pudica* in inhibiting ACE by looking at their binding interactions through molecular docking. A total of 28 bioactive compounds from *Mimosa pudica* and 3 known ACE inhibitors were docked to ACE through AutoDock 4.2.6, using standardized parameters ensuring replication across different computers, and visualized with BIOVIA. The bioavailability of the compounds was predicted using SwissADME and evaluated through adherence to Lipinski's rule of five, while the ADMET properties were predicted through pkCSM. The results showed that 13 bioactive compounds, with apigenin-7-D-glucooside and β -sitosterol topping the list, have stronger binding affinities than all three known ACE inhibitors, adhered to Lipinski's rule of five, and passed the ADMET criteria. The binding interaction between bioactive compounds from *Mimosa pudica* and ACE showed the presence of strong hydrogen and π -alkyl bonds at the active sites of the enzyme, particularly with the amino acid residues Ala354, Gln281, His353, Val380, Phe512, and His513. These suggest that these bioactive compounds of *Mimosa pudica* could be further evaluated as ACE inhibitors, which can help in addressing the current problem of expensive and inaccessible hypertension treatments.

KEYWORDS: Apigenin-7-D-glucooside, bioactive compounds, competitive inhibition, *Mimosa pudica*, molecular docking, protein-ligand interaction

1. INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a common condition characterized by the abnormal increase of blood flow pressure that can lead to cardiovascular diseases and even death.^{1,2} Known treatments include prescribed maintenance medications, such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor drugs like lisinopril, enalapril, and captopril.^{3,4}

An economic evaluation conducted in 2024 established that treating hypertension is expensive, especially due to highly priced medicine in the country.⁵ It is therefore necessary to find an affordable and common treatment for such a widespread condition. One potential solution is *Mimosa pudica*, a common weed containing bioactive compounds with anti-hypertensive properties. It is a promising alternative as it is one of the most abundant medicinal weeds in the Philippines, simplicity in its cultivation, and the lower cost of the herb compared to commercial antihypertensive drugs.⁶

The major objective of this study is to determine the effectiveness of *Mimosa pudica*'s bioactive compounds as ACE inhibitors; specifically, to assess their binding affinities in comparison to those of known ACE inhibitor drugs using molecular docking, an *in silico* setup. This study also aims to determine the bioactive compounds' bioavailability or ability to reach and be absorbed in the target sites of a human's body, as well as determine the ADMET properties.⁷ This study would benefit people in the drug development field, as results may bridge the gap between costly medication for hypertension and the need for a cost-effective and more accessible alternative.

This study involved 28 identified bioactive compounds, validated by Lagorza (2023) to have anti-hypertensive properties against non-human organisms like rats and pufferfish, and 3 ACE inhibitors from PubChem, along with ACE from the Protein Data Bank.⁶ The study, with a duration of three months, utilized OpenBabelGUI for file conversions, AutoDock 4.2.6 for molecular docking, and SwissADME and pkCSM to predict the ligands' properties. Given the *in silico* nature of this study, the results may not fully reflect real-world outcomes in an *in vitro* setting, as additional factors not accounted for in the *in silico* model could influence the results.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Molecular Docking of ACE with the Bioactive Compounds and Known ACE Inhibitors

Molecular docking was utilized to predict the interaction between ACE and the bioactive compounds, as well as the ACE inhibitors. The ACE file was downloaded from Protein Data Bank in PDB file format, then converted into PDBQT using OpenBabelGUI v2.3.1.⁸ It was then launched in AutoDock 4.2. Polar hydrogen atoms were added, water molecules were removed, missing atoms were repaired, and Gasteiger partial charges were applied and spread equally.⁹⁻¹¹

Out of 47 existing bioactive compounds, 28 were suggested relevant to the study and were therefore tested as ligands to bind with ACE. Bioactive compounds used in this study were: 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, apigenin, apigenin-7-D-glucoside, avicularin, β -sitosterol, betulinic acid, caffeic acid, catechin, chlorogenic acid, cinnamic acid, curcumin, D-mannosamine, ethyl gallate, ferulic acid, gallic acid, hyperoside, isoquercitrin, isovitexin, L-mimosine, luteolin, naringenin, orientin, protocatechuic acid, quercetin, quercitrin, rutin, and vitexin. The known ACE inhibitors used were: lisinopril, enalapril, and captopril. These were downloaded from PubChem in SDF format and converted to PDBQT format using OpenBabelGUI.

During each molecular docking procedure, each ligand file was launched in AutoDock 4.2. The root of the ligand was detected, and the number of active torsions was identified. The grid box was set up according to the values in Table 1.¹¹

Table 1 Grid Options

Grid Options	Values ^a
x-dimension	70
y-dimension	70
z-dimension	60
x center	39.895
y center	31.205
z center	31.205
red offset	-4.389
green offset	-14.611
blue offset	12.056
angstrom spacing	0.375

Source: ^aLaskar & Duttachoudhury, 2015¹³

These were then saved as a Grid Parameter File in GPF format.¹¹ AutoGrid4 was then launched, containing the grid box file to finalize these parameters for docking. The Genetic Algorithm Parameters were set according to the number of active torsions and the Number of GA Runs to 50.¹¹ The output was saved in DPF or Docking Parameter File Format with the use of Lamarckian GA. This DPF file was run to finish the docking. After docking, the final molecular docking file was generated in DLG or Docking Log File format. These procedures were then applied to the remaining ligand files, following the same customization and parameters.

2.2 Data Analysis

The properties required for evaluation for Lipinski's Rule of Five and ADMET criteria of the best conformations were predicted through the online tool, SwissADME. Running the structure downloaded from PubChem generated the mentioned properties. The bioavailability of the 28 bioactive compounds was determined through Lipinski's rule of five, shown in Table 2. These properties are necessary to determine the compounds' likelihood of oral absorption, hence these should adhere to the parameters of Lipinski's rule of five with no more than one violation.¹⁴

These bioactive compounds were further analyzed to determine whether they meet the ADMET criteria. The Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System (SMILES) was obtained from PubChem and used to predict the properties through the online tool, pkCSM.¹⁶ The predicted properties were then evaluated using the ADMET criteria shown in Table 3, which ensure that these compounds can function effectively and safely inside the body. After all dockings, the best conformation was identified by opening the resulting DLG file from each docking and selecting the lowest binding energy in the RMSD table.

Table 2 Properties for Lipinski's rule of five

Properties	Rule of Five ^a
Molecular Mass (MM)	≤ 500 g/mol
Hydrogen Bond Donors (HBD)	≤ 5
Hydrogen Bond Acceptors (HBA)	≤ 10
Partition Coefficient (PC)	≤ 5

Source: ^aOlatunde et al., 2022¹⁵

Table 3 ADMET Properties

Properties	Criteria
Human Intestinal Absorption (% Absorbed) ^a	≥ 30%
Blood-Brain Barrier Penetration (log BB) ^b	< 0 (negative value)
AMES toxicity or Carcinogenicity (Yes or No) ^c	No

Source: ^{a,c}Pires et al., 2015¹⁶; ^bWang et al., 2018¹⁷

2.3 Safety & Ethics

Due to the *in silico* nature of the study, the safety protocols to be considered are related to the use of computers. Hazards mainly consist of physical pain or headaches and eyestrain due to prolonged computer use, overheating, or electrical shock from improper charging, computer virus attacks, and access restrictions. With this, routine breaks from stationary working and checking of equipment were implemented. Up-to-date antivirus software was installed while having regular scans, and known and secure user authentication protocols were established.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Determination of Oral Bioavailability

Out of the 28 bioactive compounds, 23 compounds adhered to Lipinski's rule of five, which predicts them to be orally bioavailable. Three compounds, isovitexin, chlorogenic acid, and avicularin, were still considered orally bioavailable as they have only one violation—hydrogen bond donors should be less than or equal to 5. On the other hand, five compounds—quercitrin, hyperoside, isoquercitrin, orientin, and rutin—were found to be non-compliant, violating more than one rule.

3.2 Molecular Docking

After docking the 28 bioactive compounds to ACE, 18 compounds have a stronger binding affinity than all of the ACE inhibitors due to their low binding energies. Only one bioactive compound, which is cinnamic acid, has the same binding affinity as enalapril, while the rest of the bioactive compounds have a weaker binding affinity. The most negative score among all the generated conformations of each docked bioactive compound was listed as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Binding energies of the best conformations of the known ACE inhibitors and 18 of the bioactive compounds of *Mimosa pudica*

Known ACE inhibitors	Binding energy (kcal/mol)
Lisinopril	-6.56
Enalapril	-6.46
Captopril	-6.36
Bioactive Compounds	Binding energy (kcal/mol)
Apigenin-7-D-glucoside	-9.27
β -Sitosterol	-9.07
Betulinic acid	-8.86
Luteolin	-8.57
Apigenin	-8.07
Naringenin	-7.72
Hyperoside	-7.37
Rutin	-7.15
Ferulic Acid	-7.07
Isoquercitrin	-6.95
Vitexin	-6.90
Quercitrin	-6.86
Orientin	-6.84
Quercetin	-6.82
Isovitexin	-6.81
Caffeic Acid	-6.78
Chlorogenic Acid	-6.77
Catechin	-6.66

3.3 ADMET Properties

Out of the 28 bioactive compounds, 13 compounds adhered to Lipinski's rule of five and have stronger binding affinities than all known ACE inhibitors. These bioactive compounds also passed the ADMET criteria for antihypertensive drugs. However, one of the bioactive compounds, β -Sitosterol, showed a less-than-optimal value in one parameter: it did not meet the recommended negative log BB value. The ADMET values of these bioactive compounds are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 ADMET properties of the known ACE inhibitors and 13 bioactive compounds that passed Lipinski's rule of five and have stronger binding affinities than all known ACE inhibitors

Bioactive compounds	Properties ^a		
	Human Intestinal Absorption Numeric (% Absorbed)	Blood-Brain Barrier Penetration Numeric (log BB)	AMES toxicity (Carcinogenicity)
Known ACE Inhibitors			
Captopril	79.76900	-0.22900	No
Enalapril	43.99000	-0.69800	No
Lisinopril	13.02200	-1.15000	No
Bioactive compounds			
Apigenin-7-D-glucoside	39.06600	-1.17700	No
β-Sitosterol	94.46400	0.78100	No
Betulinic acid	99.76300	-0.32200	No
Luteolin	81.13000	-0.90700	No
Apigenin	93.25000	-0.73400	No
Naringenin	91.31000	-0.57800	No
Ferulic acid	93.68500	-0.23900	No
Vitexin	46.69500	-1.44900	No
Quercetin	77.20700	-1.09800	No
Isovitexin	64.72900	-1.37500	No
Caffeic acid	69.40700	-0.64700	No
Chlorogenic acid	36.37700	-1.40700	No
Catechin	68.82900	-1.05400	No

^a Predicted through pkCSM

3.4 Analysis of ADMET Properties

The 13 bioactive compounds that adhered to Lipinski's rule of five and have a stronger binding affinity than all known ACE inhibitors also passed the ADMET criteria for anti-hypertensive drugs. They had greater than 30% human intestinal absorption and are not AMET toxic. Only β-Sitosterol did not pass the prescribed criteria for the blood-brain barrier (BBB) penetration where it is preferred to have a negative log BB value for non-central nervous system drugs such as antihypertensives.¹⁷ However, certain antihypertensive drugs with positive log BB values may be beneficial for older adults as they have been associated with a reduced risk of developing dementia.¹⁸ This suggests that β-Sitosterol should undergo in vitro testing to determine whether its positive log BB value may have harmful effects or not.

3.5 Protein-Ligand Interaction

The protein-ligand interaction visualized through BIOVIA using the docking results between ACE and the ligands—*Mimosa pudica*'s bioactive compounds and known ACE inhibitors—showed the presence of strong hydrogen and π-alkyl bonds at the active sites of the protein. The amino acid residues of the bioactive compounds where these types of bonding are present are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Hydrogen bonding and π -alkyl interactions of ACE with the 3 known ACE inhibitors and 13 of 28 bioavailable bioactive compounds of *Mimosa pudica* that passed Lipinski's rule of five, ADMET criteria, and have stronger binding affinities than all known ACE inhibitors Ligands

Ligands	Amino Acids Involved and Interaction Distance (Å) ^a	
	Amino acids involved in hydrogen bonding (HB)	Amino acids involved in π -Alkyl
Known ACE Inhibitors		
Lisinopril	Ala354, Lys511, Gln281, His387, Glu411, Tyr523, Asp415	Val380, His383, His513, Tyr520
Enalapril	His513, Tyr523, His353, His383, Gln281, Lys511, Tyr520	Ala356, Phe512, His353 (in HB), Tyr523 (in HB), His383 (in HB)
Captopril	Lys511, Gln281, Tyr520, Cys352, His353, His513	Phe457, Tyr523
Bioavailable Bioactive Compounds		
Apigenin-7-D-glucoside	Asp377 (4.34, 4.29), Cys352 (4.04), Gln281 (5.95), Lys511 (4.93, 3.94), Phe512, Thr372 (3.87)	Cys352 (4.91), Leu161 (6.08)
β -Sitosterol	Asp453 (3.31)	Ala354 (3.15), His353 (7.23, 4.57, 5.47), His513 (6.67, 5.30), Phe457 (4.82), Phe512 (5.78), Phe527 (5.73, 7.47), Tyr523 (5.36, 5.25), Val380 (6.25), Val518 (5.64, 4.89)
Betulinic acid	Asn70 (4.22), Glu411 (4.17), Tyr523 (6.36)	His387 (5.29), His410 (5.31), Phe391 (5.94, 6.39), Phe512 (6.70), Trp357 (6.18), Val351 (4.86), Val518 (4.78, 5.26, 5.33)
Luteolin	Cys352 (4.16, 3.91), Glu162 (3.27), Leu161 (4.70), Lys511 (3.45, 5.30)	Cys352 (4.94), Leu161 (4.03, 5.41, 5.51)
Apigenin	Cys352 (3.91), Lys511 (5.11), Leu161 (4.93), Glu162 (3.39)	Leu161 (3.99, 5.62), Cys352 (4.80)
Naringenin	Glu162 (3.22), Lys511 (5.53)	Leu161 (4.38)
Ferulic Acid	Ala149 (1.98), Tyr146 (2.39)	Cys352 (4.18), Leu161 (4.17)
Vitexin	Ala354 (3.58), Asn277 (5.94), Gln281 (5.54, 5.19), Glu162 (5.59), Glu411 (4.16), Tyr520 (4.63, 6.08)	Val380 (5.67)
Quercetin	Arg348 (6.30), Asp346 (3.67), Glu342 (2.79, 3.15), Leu341 (4.91), Lys338 (4.57, 4.90), Thr345 (2.95), Trp67 (5.07), Ser339 (4.75)	Met340 (4.30, 5.36), Pro344 (4.67)
Isovitexin	Glu162 (5.44), Glu411 (4.59), Gly276 (4.26, 4.64), Met278 (3.58), Tyr523 (5.72)	Ala354 (6.47, 4.60), Val380 (6.34)
Caffeic Acid	Ala149 (3.12), Glu349 (3.55), Leu161 (4.22), Tyr146 (3.77)	Cys352 (6.74), Leu161 [in HB] (4.52)
Chlorogenic Acid	Ala149 (3.62), Glu162 (4.33, 5.45), His353 (2.94), Leu161 (4.39), Ser147 (4.78)	Cys352 (4.78), Leu161 (4.37)
Catechin	Arg348 (6.12), Asp346 (3.61), Glu342 (3.66), Leu341 (5.95), Lys338 (4.87), Met340 (5.00), Ser339 (4.74), Thr345 (3.00), Trp67 (5.27)	Met340 (3.92)

^aVisualized through BIOVIA

3.6 Analysis of Interactions

The stronger binding affinity of the 18 bioactive compounds is attributed to key active-site amino acid residues of ACE—Ala354, Gln281, His353, Val380, Phe512, and His513—identified in previous studies by Liu et al. (2020) on black ginseng and Su et al. (2021) on ACE-inhibitory peptides from *Takifugu flavidus* (yellowbelly pufferfish).¹⁹⁻²⁰ These amino acid residues are also present in the interaction between known ACE inhibitors and the ACE. The bioactive compounds with a stronger binding affinity than all known ACE inhibitors have similar key amino acid residues as previously mentioned in the active sites. The only difference between the bioactive compounds with a stronger binding affinity, like apigenin-7-D-glucoside, as compared to other bioactive compounds with weaker binding affinities is that they contain more of the key amino acid residues present on the key active site, which was demonstrated by the two previously mentioned studies that used naturally produced ACE inhibitors. The interactions of apigenin-7-D-glucoside with ACE, shown in Figure 1, also have similarities to those of the known ACE inhibitor, Captopril, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Structure of Apigenin-7-D-glucoside with its interaction with ACE residues—Lys511, Gln281, His353, and His513—which are also present in Captopril. The red boxes enclose carbonyl, carboxyl, and hydroxyl groups.

Figure 2 Structure of Captopril with its interaction with ACE. Captopril forms hydrogen bonds with ACE residues—Lys511, Gln281, His353, and His513—providing a basis for the key active-site amino acid residues of ACE.

There is also a similarity in the structure of the bioactive compound with the strongest binding affinity, apigenin-7-D-glucoside, and the known ACE inhibitor, Lisinopril, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 3. Both compounds have the presence of many oxygen and nitrogen heteroatoms contributing to their polarity, and functional groups such as hydroxyl, carbonyl, and carboxyl groups, enclosed in red squares (See Figure 1 and Figure 3), which form the hydrogen bonds with ACE. These hydrogen bonds likely make a significant contribution to the increased binding affinity of the bioactive compounds with ACE, which explains the observed low binding energies.

Figure 3 Structure of Lisinopril contains similar functional groups as Apigenin-7-D-glucoside. The red boxes enclose carbonyl, carboxyl, and hydroxyl groups.

4. CONCLUSION

The 13 bioactive compounds of *Mimosa pudica* attained a stronger binding affinity than all known ACE inhibitors, adhered to the Lipinski's rule of five, and met the ADMET criteria, with only β -Sitosterol not following the optimal log BB value. Additionally, these bioactive compounds also target the same key active sites that the existing ACE inhibitors target. Therefore, it can be concluded that a total of 13 bioactive compounds of *Mimosa pudica* are effective in inhibiting ACE, are orally absorbable, and have safe ADMET properties. These findings suggest that *Mimosa pudica* may serve as a cost-effective source of ACE inhibitors for hypertensive patients. It is now recommended to conduct *in vitro* research due to its *in silico* nature to further confirm the drug properties of the bioactive compounds. It is also recommended to compute its half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) value to properly measure the potency of its inhibition through an *in vitro* and *in silico* approach for the determination of parameters and calculation using various software, respectively.

5. AUTHOR INFORMATION

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Author Contributions

A.D.G. F.E.L.R., and A.C.D.T. all contributed to the conception, design, data analysis, and writing of the manuscript. A.D.G. and F.E.L.R. conducted the molecular docking, visualization of interactions, and prediction of ADMET properties. A.C.D.T. and F.E.L.R. conducted the search and validation of the bioactive compounds used through different research journals found on the internet.

A.D.G. conducted the evaluation of adherence to Lipinski's rule of five. A.C.D.T. contributed significantly to the Results and Discussion sections, which include the interpretation of the resulting binding energies and analysis of the protein-ligand interactions.

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